

Counterattack Initiation Zones Account for Apparent Differences Between Men's and Women's Professional Soccer: Evidence From Japan's J-League and WE League

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Abstract

This study investigated whether apparent differences in counterattack characteristics between men's and women's professional soccer reflect true executional differences or are primarily driven by variations in initiation zones. All counterattack goals from Japan's J-League (men) and WE League (women) were analyzed. Counterattacks were classified according to initiation zone (defensive, middle, or attacking third), and three variables were quantified: attacking time from ball recovery to goal, number of attacking players involved, and number of passes. Chi-square analyses revealed significant differences in the distribution of initiation zones between leagues, with the J-League showing a more balanced distribution and the WE League exhibiting a greater proportion of counterattacks initiated in advanced areas. However, generalized linear models showed no significant League \times Zone interaction effects for attacking time, number of players, or number of passes. This indicates that execution patterns were broadly similar across leagues once initiation zone was considered. Overall gender differences in counterattack metrics therefore appear to largely reflect compositional effects related to initiation zones rather than fundamental differences in tactical execution. These findings highlight the importance of accounting for spatial context when comparing tactical performance between men's and women's soccer.

Keywords: Counterattack, Soccer tactics, Gender comparison, Initiation zone

INTRODUCTION

Counterattacks represent one of the most decisive tactical elements in modern soccer, characterized by rapid transitions from defensive to offensive phases that exploit spatial disorganization before opponents can re-establish their defensive structure (Bekkers & Sahasrabudhe, 2024; Hughes & Franks, 2005; Tenga, Holme, Ronglan, & Bahr, 2010a, 2010b). Spatiotemporal performance analyses have shown that effective counterattacks require coordinated integration of physical, technical, and tactical components, and gender-specific models indicate that transition speed and spatial positioning are key determinants of success (Bekkers & Sahasrabudhe, 2024; Rochoael & Praça, 2024).

Growing evidence highlights technical–tactical differences between men's and women's elite soccer. Pappalardo et al. reported distinct patterns in play accuracy and ball-possession recovery time between genders (Pappalardo, Rossi, Natilli, & Cintia, 2021), while Garnica-Caparrós and Memmert identified action-level features—such as ball recoveries, passes, and tackles—that systematically differentiate male and female playing styles (Garnica-Caparrós & Memmert, 2021). Comparative analyses of goal-creating sequences have revealed specific gender differences relevant to counterattack dynamics. Mitrotasios et al. examined UEFA Champions League matches and reported that men's teams produced longer possession sequences with more passes (6.36 vs. 4.48) and faster pass tempo (3.27 s vs. 4.01 s per pass), while women's teams initiated more possessions in the opponent's half (64.78% vs. 38.07%) and faced higher defensive pressure at possession initiation (Mitrotasios, González Rodenas, Armatas, & Aranda, 2021). Espada et al. similarly observed that Portuguese women's teams more frequently regained possession through interceptions in advanced zones and generated goals via fast attacks, whereas men's teams relied more on dispossessing tackles (Espada et al., 2018). Additional studies have documented tactical evolution in women's football, including increases in passing accuracy and the effectiveness of fast organized attacks (Althoff, Kroihner, & Hennig, 2010; Bransen & Davis, 2024; Casal, Losada, Dios, & Arda, 2021; Craven, Oxenham, & Ranaweera, 2025).

Despite these advances, several critical gaps remain. First, no studies have directly quantified the time elapsed from ball recovery to goal during counterattacks between genders, a key performance indicator for evaluating transition efficiency. Second, the number of attacking players involved—a fundamental structural component of counterattack organization—has not been systematically compared. Third, previous work has rarely integrated temporal, spatial, and tactical variables within a comprehensive analytical framework. Moreover, existing studies have focused overwhelmingly on European or North American competitions (Althoff et al., 2010; Bransen & Davis, 2024; Casal et al., 2021; Craven et al., 2025; Espada et al., 2018; Garnica-Caparrós & Memmert, 2021; Mitrotasios et al., 2021; Pappalardo et al., 2021), leaving Asian professional leagues, including men's (J-League) and women's (WE League) professional leagues in Japan, completely unexplored.

To address these gaps, the present study provides the first comparative analysis of counterattack characteristics between men's and women's professional leagues in Asia. Using match data from J-League and WE League, we applied an integrated four-metric framework: (1) initiation zones, (2) time duration from ball recovery to goal, (3) number of attacking players involved, and (4) passes executed. Based on prior research (Bransen & Davis, 2024; Craven et al., 2025; Espada et al., 2018; Mitrotasios et al., 2021), we hypothesized that: (H1) WE League counterattacks would more frequently originate from advanced areas; (H2) WE League counterattacks would exhibit shorter durations due to more frequent initiation from forward positions; (H3) J-League counterattacks would involve a greater number of attacking players; and (H4) J-League counterattacks would include more passes. This comprehensive approach allows us to examine individual tactical dimensions and their interrelationships, and to determine whether patterns identified in European leagues generalize to Japanese

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professional soccer. The findings will provide evidence-based insights for coaching, talent development, and performance analysis within an underrepresented geographic context.

METHOD

Data Source and Sample

This observational study analyzed all goals scored in two major Japanese professional soccer leagues to compare counterattacking characteristics between men's and women's competitions. The dataset consisted of every match played during the 2023 and 2024 Meiji Yasuda J1 League seasons (J-League, 686 matches) and all matches from the 2022–23 and 2023–24 WE League seasons (WE League, 242 matches). Goal scenes were obtained from publicly accessible match videos on the DAZN Japan YouTube Channel, the WE League Official YouTube Channel, and other official sources on YouTube. Only those goals for which the entire attacking sequence—from the moment of ball recovery until the goal—could be clearly observed were included. Among all 1,783 J-League goals and 613 WE League goals, five J-League goals and four WE League goals were excluded due to incomplete visibility of the attacking process, leaving 1,778 and 609 goals respectively for analysis.

Classification of Attacking Types

All goals were classified into attacking types based on the conceptual framework established by Tenga et al. (2010) (Tenga et al., 2010a). According to this framework, counterattacks were operationalized as direct-play sequences that began with ball recovery during open play and progressed by either exploiting or attempting to exploit defensive imbalance throughout the entire sequence, or by creating or attempting to create imbalance through an early penetrative action such as a first or second pass or dribble. Exploiting imbalance was understood as progressing toward goal in a manner that prevented the defending team from regaining a high degree of defensive organization before the end of the possession. Such sequences typically proceeded relatively quickly. In contrast, possession-based elaborate attacks were defined as sequences that also began with ball recovery in open play but progressed without utilizing or attempting to utilize defensive imbalance, or by creating imbalance only through later penetrative actions (third or subsequent passes or dribbles). In these situations, the defending team was considered able to re-establish a high degree of structural balance before the conclusion of the possession. Goals resulting from closed-play restarts, including corner kicks, penalty kicks, free kicks, and long throws, were categorized separately. Rebound situations such as one- or two-touch finishes following defensive clearances were classified as “other,” as they did not correspond clearly to either direct-play counterattacks or elaborate possession attacks. Initial classification was carried out by the first author, and ambiguous cases were resolved collectively through consensus among three analysts with more than ten years of competitive playing experience. To assess intra-rater reliability, 10% of goals were randomly selected and re-coded two weeks after the initial coding. For attacking types, Cohen's kappa coefficient was calculated, demonstrating excellent agreement ($\kappa = 0.91$). Only goals classified as counterattacks were included in the subsequent analyses.

Measures of Counterattack Characteristics

For all goals classified as counterattacks (J-League: 333 goals, WE League: 100 goals), the initiation zone was identified by determining the precise location of ball recovery using visible field markings, lines, and mowing patterns. Based on standard pitch division, the field was separated into three horizontal thirds: the attacking third (AT), middle third (MT), and defending third (DT). For each counterattack, attacking time, the number of attacking players and the number of completed passes were measured. Attacking time was defined as the duration (in seconds) from the moment of ball recovery initiating a counterattack to the moment the goal was scored. Ball recovery was identified as the first controlled action by the attacking team following a turnover of possession, including interceptions, tackles, or recoveries of loose balls. The number of attacking players was defined as the

total number of attacking team players who touched the ball at least once, with repeated touches by the same player counted only once. The number of passes was defined as the total count of completed passes executed by the attacking team during the counterattack sequence, from ball recovery to goal completion.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics 24 (SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA). Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

To examine the distribution of counterattack origins across pitch zones, χ^2 goodness-of-fit tests were conducted separately for the J-League and WE League. Standardized residuals were calculated to identify zones with significantly higher or lower frequencies than expected. Differences in the distribution of counterattack origins between the two leagues were assessed using a χ^2 test of independence.

Attacking time, number of attacking players, and passes exhibited violations of normality and homoscedasticity based on Shapiro–Wilk tests and Levene’s tests; therefore, these variables were analyzed using generalized linear models (GLM). For attacking time, a Gamma distribution with a log link function was applied, whereas a Poisson distribution with a log link was used for the number of attacking players and passes. Each model included League (J-League vs. WE League), Zone (AT, MT, DT), and their interaction as fixed factors. Type III likelihood-based Wald χ^2 statistics were used to evaluate the significance of main effects and interactions.

When a significant main effect was observed, pairwise comparisons of estimated marginal (EM) means were conducted with Bonferroni adjustment. In addition, overall comparisons between leagues (ALL) for attacking time, number of attacking players, and passes were also performed using GLM with the same distributional assumptions applied to each variable.

EM means with 95% confidence intervals (CI) were reported for all GLM-derived outcomes.

RESULTS

A χ^2 goodness-of-fit test showed significant differences in counterattack frequencies across pitch zones in both leagues. In the J-League (AT: 122 (37%), MT: 148 (44%), DT: 63 (19%)), MT was overrepresented (+3.51) and DT underrepresented (−4.56) ($\chi^2(2) = 34.18, p < 0.001$). In the WE League (AT: 58 (58%), MT: 37 (37%), DT: 5 (5%)), AT was overrepresented (+4.27) and DT markedly underrepresented (−4.91) ($\chi^2(2) = 42.74, p < 0.001$) (Table 1). A χ^2 test of independence further confirmed that the distribution of counterattack origins differed between leagues ($\chi^2(2) = 18.93, p < 0.001$), with the WE League showing relatively more counterattacks from AT and fewer from DT.

Table 1. Counterattack frequencies by pitch zone

League	Zone			χ^2 goodness-of-fit tests				
	AT	MT	DT	χ^2 (df=2)	p-value	AT (stdres)	MT (stdres)	DT (stdres)
J-League	122 (37%)	148 (44%)	63 (19%)	34.18	< 0.001	1.04	3.51	−4.56
WE League	58 (58%)	37 (37%)	5 (5%)	42.74	< 0.001	4.27	0.64	−4.91

AT, attacking third; MT, middle third; DT, defensive third.

Because normality and homoscedasticity were not met for attacking time, number of attacking players, and passes, these variables were analyzed using GLM. A Gamma distribution with a log link was applied for attacking time, and a Poisson distribution with a log link was applied for attacking players and passes (Table 2).

Table 2. Generalized linear model results of counterattack characteristics

Variables	League	Zone			P-value of GLM (Wald χ^2)		
		AT	MT	DT	Interaction (League*Zone)	Main effect	
		(95% CI)	(95% CI)	(95% CI)		League	Zone
Attacking time, sec	J-League	3.36±0.11 (3.16-3.58)	7.18±0.21 ^a (6.78-7.60)	11.93±0.53 ^{a,b} (10.93-13.03)	0.59 (1.07)	0.87 (0.03)	< 0.01 (399.63)
	WE League	3.44±0.16 (3.14-3.77)	6.73±0.39 ^a (6.00-7.55)	12.06±1.91 ^a (8.84-16.46)			
Attacking players, n	J-League	1.84±0.21 (1.48-2.30)	2.68±0.26 (2.22-3.24)	3.32±0.48 (2.50-4.40)	0.93 (0.15)	0.55 (0.36)	< 0.05 (6.98)
	WE League	1.71±0.28 (1.23-2.36)	2.22±0.44 (1.50-3.27)	3.00±1.55 (1.09-8.25)			
Passes, n	J-League	0.89±0.12 (0.69-1.16)	1.85±0.19 ^a (1.52-2.26)	2.56±0.38 ^a (1.91-3.42)	0.91 (0.19)	0.22 (1.50)	< 0.01 (20.41)
	WE League	0.72±0.15 (0.49-1.08)	1.30±0.28 (0.847-1.99)	2.00±1.10 (0.68-5.85)			

AT, attacking third; MT, middle third; DT, defensive third. Values are presented as the EM mean ± SE. a and b, significant difference ($p < 0.05$) compared to AT and MT, respectively.

For attacking time, the GLM showed no significant interaction between League and Zone (Wald $\chi^2 = 1.07$, $p = 0.59$). The main effect of League was not significant (Wald $\chi^2 = 0.03$, $p = 0.87$), whereas the main effect of Zone was significant (Wald $\chi^2 = 399.63$, $p < 0.01$). Bonferroni-adjusted pairwise comparisons indicated that MT and DT were significantly longer than AT in both leagues, and DT in J-League was significantly longer than MT. In the overall comparison (ALL), attacking time was significantly longer (Wald $\chi^2 = 17.89$, $p < 0.01$) in the J-League (6.68±0.21 sec [95% CI, 6.29-7.10]) than in the WE League (5.10±0.29 sec [95% CI, 4.56-5.68]).

For the number of attacking players, no significant interaction was found (Wald $\chi^2 = 0.15$, $p = 0.93$), and the main effect of League was not significant (Wald $\chi^2 = 0.36$, $p = 0.55$). In contrast, the main effect of Zone was significant (Wald $\chi^2 = 6.98$, $p < 0.05$). Although EM means increased from AT to MT to DT, Bonferroni-adjusted comparisons were not significant; however, DT tended to be higher than AT in the J-League ($p = 0.07$). For the ALL comparison, the number of attacking players tended (Wald $\chi^2 = 3.02$, $p = 0.08$) to be higher in the J-League (2.50±0.16 [95% CI, 2.20-2.83]) than in the WE League (1.96±0.24 [95% CI, 1.54-2.49]).

For the number of passes, the interaction term was not significant (Wald $\chi^2 = 0.19$, $p = 0.91$). The main effect of League was not significant (Wald $\chi^2 = 1.50$, $p = 0.22$), whereas the main effect of Zone was significant (Wald $\chi^2 = 20.41$, $p < 0.01$). MT and DT were significantly greater than AT in J-League. In the ALL comparison, the number of passes was significantly greater (Wald $\chi^2 = 9.70$, $p < 0.01$) in the J-League (1.63±0.11 [95% CI, 1.43-1.87]) than in the WE League (1.00±0.14 [95% CI, 0.76-1.32]).

Figure 1 Attacking time, number of attacking players and passes in the J-League (white) and WE League (black) from each pitch zone (AT, MT and DT).

Values are presented as the EM mean \pm SE. a and b, significant difference by the generalized linear model ($p < 0.05$) compared to AT and MT, respectively. *, significant difference by the generalized linear model ($p < 0.05$) compared to WE League.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The present study examined whether apparent gender differences in professional soccer counterattacks could be explained by differences in the spatial distribution of initiation zones rather than by differences in execution characteristics. Overall, the results supported H1, H2, and H4, while H3 received only trend-level support. The distribution of counterattack initiation zones differed significantly between leagues, with J-League teams initiating more counterattacks from the defensive third and WE League teams more from the forward third. Aggregate comparisons indicated significantly longer attacking time and more passes in the J-League, with a trend toward a greater number of attacking players. However, when initiation zone was included in the models,

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no significant league \times zone interactions were observed. This suggests that once spatial context is considered, counterattack execution patterns appear broadly similar between the two leagues.

The absence of League \times Zone interactions constitutes a cornerstone finding of this study. For attacking time, Zone effects were highly significant ($p < 0.01$), whereas League effects were non-significant ($p = 0.87$). The same pattern was observed for the number of attacking players and the number of passes, with significant Zone effects but non-significant League effects and no League \times Zone interactions. This divergence between zone-controlled and aggregated analyses exemplifies a compositional effect: WE League's concentration in the attacking third (58% vs. J-League's 37%) naturally produces shorter average durations because AT-initiated attacks require less distance coverage. Accordingly, the overall league difference arises largely from distributional weighting rather than different behaviors within contexts. This challenges assumptions about gender differences in soccer tactics, suggesting that execution patterns appeared broadly similar once spatial context is controlled.

WE League's forward-biased pattern may reflect more aggressive high-pressing strategies. Espada et al. (Espada et al., 2018) reported that Portuguese women's teams recovered possession preferentially in offensive zones via interceptions, while Mitrotasios et al. (Mitrotasios et al., 2021) found women's UEFA Champions League teams initiated 64.78% of sequences in the opponent's half versus 38.07% for men's teams. Kubayi (Kubayi, 2022) analyzed the 2019 FIFA Women's World Cup and found counterattacks from forward positions produced higher scoring rates (12.7% vs. 7.5% for organized attacks), suggesting that women's teams may have adapted defensive positioning to maximize high-value ball recoveries.

In contrast, the J-League's more balanced distribution of counterattack initiation may reflect conditions that allow teams to initiate transitions from deeper zones. Physical and technical factors may partly explain this pattern. Men's football is characterized by faster pass tempo and greater passing volume (Casal et al., 2021; Hjelm, 2011; Mitrotasios et al., 2021), suggesting a higher capacity to execute rapid passing sequences under match conditions. Although controlled technical tests report no clear sex differences in isolated long-pass accuracy (Sørensen, Haugen, & van den Tillaar, 2022), biomechanical analyses indicate gender-specific lower-extremity kinematics that may influence long-distance passing under defensive pressure (Althoff & Hennig, 2017; Barnett, van Beurden, Morgan, Brooks, & Beard, 2010). Thus, even if isolated accuracy is comparable, execution quality for long-distance passing under match conditions may differ. Moreover, contextual match factors appear critical: men's teams tend to initiate possession under lower defensive pressure and from deeper zones, whereas women's teams more frequently regain possession in advanced areas and face higher immediate pressure, potentially constraining long-distance build-up play (Casal et al., 2021; Gonzalez-Rodenas et al., 2017; Mitrotasios et al., 2021). In addition, tactical culture may contribute to league-specific patterns. Empirical analyses of J-League matches have demonstrated structured positional support and systematic build-up behaviors in defensive and middle thirds, reflecting a possession-oriented approach to attack construction (Matsubara et al., 2022; Mitani & Asahi, 2022; Suda & Asahi, 2018). Such tactical characteristics may enable teams to initiate counterattacks from multiple pitch zones rather than relying primarily on high-position ball recovery. Collectively, these findings suggest that the J-League's balanced distribution of counterattack origins reflects an interaction between technical capacities, pressure environments at possession initiation, and a tactical emphasis on structured possession-based play.

The absence of League \times Zone interactions demonstrates that fundamental counterattack dynamics—how time, player involvement, and passes scale with distance—are broadly similar between genders. Both men's and women's teams face similar structural constraints, whereby greater distance necessitates longer time, more intermediate actions, and additional players. This suggests that counterattack execution is governed by shared fundamental principles rather than gender-specific mechanisms, with important practical implications. These findings suggest that some tactical principles may be transferable across genders, as tactical patterns may be

similar once spatial context is established. Drills designed to optimize counterattacks from specific zones may therefore be applicable to both male and female players (Rochael & Praça, 2024). Gender-specific training may therefore be less critical, and coaches may instead focus on context-specific training while recognizing that the primary gender difference lies in frequency distribution across contexts rather than context-specific execution.

This study has several limitations. Our analysis focused on successful counterattacks only, which may introduce survival bias. We did not measure defensive tactics (pressing intensity, defensive line height), and contextual factors such as score differential, match time, team quality were not controlled. Furthermore, the observational design precludes causal conclusions, and experimental or intervention-based studies are therefore needed (Rochael & Praça, 2024). Future research should track the evolution of the WE League over multiple seasons, compare counterattack effectiveness across initiation zones using expected goals (xG) metrics (Biermann, Yang, Memmert, Wieland, & Timmer, 2024), conduct cross-regional comparisons, and apply machine learning approaches to model complex tactical interactions (Bekkers & Sahasrabudhe, 2024). Further, the interpretation of zone-specific estimates for DT counterattacks in the WE League should be cautious because of the very small sample size. Finally, integrating physiological data may help clarify whether physical factors contribute to observed differences in initiation zone distributions.

This study suggests that gender differences in counterattacking between the J-League and WE League are primarily compositional, arising from different spatial distributions rather than tactical execution. Once initiation zone is controlled, men's and women's teams employ largely similar counterattacking patterns, which challenge assumptions of fundamental gender differences in tactical execution and redirect attention toward factors shaping initiation distributions. Our integrated four-metric framework provides a comprehensive approach for future research. Practically, these findings suggest that coaches and analysts should pay close attention to ball recovery positioning when interpreting counterattack performance, because differences in aggregate metrics may largely reflect initiation-zone distribution. As the first comprehensive comparison of counterattack characteristics in Asian professional soccer, this research establishes a foundation for understanding tactical performance across genders and provides evidence-based guidance for coaching practice.

Declarations

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this study.

Ethical Statement

The principles of scientific research and publication ethics were followed throughout the conduct of this study, including the research design, data collection process, data analysis, interpretation of findings, and preparation of the manuscript. All procedures were conducted in accordance with ethical research standards, and all sources used in the study have been appropriately cited in accordance with academic writing principles.

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Author Contribution Rate

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REFERENCES

- Althoff, K., & Hennig, E. (2017). Biomechanical and motor performance differences between female and male soccer players. *Football Biomechanics* (pp. 101-113).
- Althoff, K., Kroihner, J., & Hennig, E. M. (2010). A soccer game analysis of two World Cups: playing behavior between elite female and male soccer players. *Footwear Science*, 2(1), 51-56. doi:10.1080/19424281003685686
- Barnett, L. M., van Beurden, E., Morgan, P. J., Brooks, L. O., & Beard, J. R. (2010). Gender differences in motor skill proficiency from childhood to adolescence: a longitudinal study. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 81(2), 162-170. doi:10.1080/02701367.2010.10599663
- Bekkers, J., & Sahasrabudhe, A. (2024). A Graph Neural Network deep-dive into successful counterattacks, arXiv:2411.17450. Retrieved from <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2024arXiv241117450B>
- Biermann, H., Yang, W., Memmert, D., Wieland, F.-G., & Timmer, J. (2024). *Quantification of Turnover Danger with xCounter*. Paper presented at the International Workshop on Machine Learning and Data Mining for Sports Analytics. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-53833-9_4
- Bransen, L., & Davis, J. (2024). A data-driven analysis of the technical and tactical evolution of elite women's football. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 19(6), 2449-2459. doi:10.1177/17479541241257809
- Casal, C., Losada, J., Dios, R., & Arda, A. (2021). Gender differences in technical-tactical behaviour of La Liga Spanish football teams. *Journal of Human Sport and Exercise*, 16, 37-52. doi:10.14198/jhse.2021.161.04
- Craven, L., Oxenham, P., & Ranaweera, J. (2025). Analysis of attacking styles and goal-scoring in the 2021/22 Women's Super League. *PloS One*, 20(2), e0318929. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0318929
- Espada, M., Fernandes, C., Martins, C., Leitao, H., Figueiredo, T., & Santos, F. (2018). Goal characterization after ball recovery in players of both genders of first league soccer teams in Portugal. *Human Movement Special Issues*, 73-81. doi:10.5114/hm.2018.81288
- Garnica-Caparrós, M., & Memmert, D. (2021). Understanding gender differences in professional European football through machine learning interpretability and match actions data. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 10805. doi:10.1038/s41598-021-90264-w
- Gonzalez-Rodenas, J., Lopez-Bondia, I., Calabuig, F., Pérez-Turpin, J. A., & Aranda, R. (2017). Creation of goal scoring opportunities by means of different types of offensive actions in US major league soccer. *Human Movement Special Issues*, 106-116. doi:10.5114/hm.2017.73616
- Hjelm, J. (2011). The bad female football player: women's football In Sweden. *Soccer & Society*, 12, 143-158. doi:10.1080/14660970.2011.548352
- Hughes, M., & Franks, I. (2005). Analysis of passing sequences, shots and goals in soccer. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 23(5), 509-514. doi:10.1080/02640410410001716779
- Kubayi, A. (2022). The Creation of Goal-Scoring Opportunities at The 2019 FIFA Women's World Cup. *J Hum Kinet*, 82, 165-172. doi:10.2478/hukin-2022-0043
- Matsubara, H., Noriyuki, K., & Nomura, T. (2022). A Study on Support Play in Soccer Games: Relationship between Player Positioning and Zone. *Advances in Physical Education*, 12, 271-282. doi:10.4236/ape.2022.123021
- Mitani, S., & Asahi, Y. (2022, 2022//). *Characteristic Analysis of Midfielder in Japanese Professional Football League (J1 League) Using Grouping and Tactical Analysis*. Paper presented at the Human Interface and the Management of Information: Visual and Information Design, Cham.
- Mitrotasios, M., González Rodenas, J., Armatas, V., & Aranda, R. (2021). Creating Goal Scoring Opportunities in Men and Women UEFA Champions League Soccer Matches. Tactical Similarities and Differences. *Retos: Nuevas Tendencias en Educación Física, Deporte y Recreación*, 154-161. doi:10.47197/retos.v43i0.88203
- Pappalardo, L., Rossi, A., Natilli, M., & Cintia, P. (2021). Explaining the difference between men's and women's football. *PloS One*, 16(8), e0255407. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0255407
- Rochael, M., & Praça, G. M. (2024). Designing small-sided games for counter-attack training in youth soccer. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 19(2), 687-697. doi:10.1177/17479541231170830

Cited in: Miyazawa, T., Yamauchi, R., Mizutani, M., & Ichikawa, D. (2026). Counterattack initiation zones account for apparent differences between men's and women's professional soccer: Evidence from Japan's J-League and WE League. *Nortis Journal of Sports Sciences*, 2(3), 16–25.

Sørensen, A., Haugen, E. C., & van den Tillaar, R. (2022). Is There a Sex Difference in Technical Skills among Youth Soccer Players in Norway? *Sports*, 10(4), 50.

Suda, T., & Asahi, Y. (2018, 2018//). *Analysis of Factor of Scoring of Japanese Professional Football League*. Paper presented at the Human Interface and the Management of Information. Interaction, Visualization, and Analytics, Cham.

Tenga, A., Holme, I., Ronglan, L. T., & Bahr, R. (2010a). Effect of playing tactics on achieving score-box possessions in a random series of team possessions from Norwegian professional soccer matches. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 28(3), 245-255. doi:10.1080/02640410903502766

Tenga, A., Holme, I., Ronglan, L. T., & Bahr, R. (2010b). Effect of playing tactics on goal scoring in Norwegian professional soccer. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 28(3), 237-244. doi:10.1080/02640410903502774